

HVG Position Paper for the Therapy Sciences

Contemporary therapy is effective, efficient, person-centred and participation-oriented. Occupational therapy, speech and language therapy and physiotherapy (hereafter referred to as OT-SLT-PT) are socially relevant and an essential component of sustainable healthcare. The therapy sciences form part of allied health professions research, leading research in these particular fields of professional activity. They evaluate, improve and explore health promotion, disease prevention and treatment as well as appropriate guidance and support of people. If the qualified therapists themselves do not ask research questions and pursue research interests that generate reliable professional knowledge, then who would?

This position paper of the Research Commission of the HVG e.V. was developed as a reference to the research landscape of OT-SLT-PT. It is intended as an argumentation aid, both within the aforementioned professional groups and outward-facing, in order to improve the conditions for the therapy sciences and therapeutic research.

Professionalisation through academisation

The need for excellent and innovative healthcare is obvious in the light of ageing societies, worsening environmental problems, the increase in chronic and non-communicable diseases and multimorbidity [1]. Excellence, in turn, requires academically trained and experienced therapists. They must be equipped with the appropriate decision-making skills, to expand the evidence base and further develop OT-SLT-PT in a future-oriented manner.

More graduates alone cannot compensate for the increasing shortage of advanced practitioners. Targeted use of resources and the utilisation of new (digital) technologies are required. At the same time, a focus on promoting the health literacy of patients and clients is key: therapists act as multipliers in the context of professional health literacy and translate professional knowledge into applicable health information [2] [3]. The WHO emphasises the importance of health literacy in improving global health and identifies it as a central priority in the 'Shanghai Declaration on Health Promotion' [4].

In order to achieve the health-related Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations, WHO promotes Primary Health Care as the central approach for equitable, resource-efficient, needs-orientated and empowering care for the population [5]. Rehabilitation services form part of Universal Health Coverage. In this context, the WHO World Rehabilitation Alliance [6] highlights the need for interprofessional and multidisciplinary collaboration.

The majority of OT-SLT-PT practitioners in Germany worked in outpatient settings in 2021 (speech and language therapy: 75%; physiotherapy: 74% and occupational therapy: 49%) [7]. They may therefore be considered as primary healthcare providers. However, the conceptual integration of such AHPs in primary care needs to be further developed in Germany [8]. At the same time, carrying out research projects and implementing results in the decentralised outpatient therapeutic setting is very challenging in structural terms. This is where research-savvy, networked and team-oriented practitioners are particularly needed.

Therapeutic roles and fields of practice framing research

Therapists are part of the Allied Health Professions and their scientific contributions are embedded in international health and participation research. They may work in social care and community settings, but mostly represent independent specialisms in almost all fields of institutional health care. Therapists work with people of all age groups and fulfil important functions along the entire continuum of care, i.e. health promotion and prevention, diagnosis and treatment, rehabilitation and reducing dependency on nursing, and palliation. However, professional practice predominantly centres on participation and quality of life for people with acute, chronic and long-term health conditions and disorders.

Professional expertise in OT-SLT-PT arises from various competences that are linked to different roles. Seven professional roles in medicine have originally been described in the CanMEDS - Canadian Medical Education Directives for Specialists [9]: Medical Expert, Professional, Communicator, Collaborator, Leader, Health Advocate, Scholar. These roles have since been adapted internationally for various professions in the healthcare system. In German-speaking countries, this was done as part of the BMBF-funded project 'Aufstieg durch Bildung' [10], or in a paper addressing the Rectors' Conference of the Swiss Universities of Applied Sciences [11], for example. The model is also used to describe entry-level competences of qualified practice: the competence profile developed by the German Association of Occupational Therapy e.V. (DVE) uses an adaptation of the CanMEDS with seven domains [12].

The therapeutic roles or domains can be used as a perspective to frame the research interests of the therapy sciences. They provide a variety of connections between theory and practice. They can reflect the complexity of care needs and requirements - from the level of individual therapy to taking influence in society. Each of the roles can represent an entry point for empirical research, the results of which may lead to professional and interprofessional recommendations for action, models and theories. In science, theories offer the opportunity to formulate testable hypotheses, to generate diverse research results and systematise them as profession-related knowledge. Therapeutic models are important in reducing complexity and may provide practical concepts for care. In addition, both research and practice require suitable outcome measures and respective assessment tools for data collection. These need to be developed, or translated and adapted accordingly. Hence, research activities correspond with professional practice in a multiple and reciprocal manner.

Research levels and methodological spectrum of therapy sciences

Therapists conduct research at all levels of healthcare (see Fig. 1), related to the areas of their specialist expertise and to the fields of activity of their professions. Research activities span from the pre-micro level of cell functions and tissue structures to the macro level of national healthcare systems and international healthcare strategies. The therapeutic, mostly personal, interaction with patients or clients is the focus of research at the micro level. At the meso level, therapists conduct research into their functions and services in the German healthcare, social and education systems, and into their being part of the national health workforce.

The overriding aim of therapeutic activity is to promote self-determined social participation, health-related competence and quality of life for patients and service users. Interaction with individuals or groups, taking into account individual life situations, often including relatives and friends, must

therefore be central in therapeutic research. Due to the fundamental participation-orientation of OT-SLT-PT, participatory and interprofessional approaches also play an important role in their research. In this respect, the therapy sciences form a bridge between biomedical and public health research.

Fig. 1: Levels and areas of therapy sciences in occupational therapy, speech/language therapy and physiotherapy (based on [13])

Therapists influence body structures, body functions, activities and contextual factors in order to improve the participation of individuals - in the sense of the International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) and its underlying bio-psycho-social model of health [14]. The entry points and emphasis of therapeutic practice within the ICF framework may vary between the professions of OT-SLT-PT. New opportunities and challenges for therapeutic action and communication arise from digitalisation, for example in the adaptation and use of (increasingly digital) assistive technologies. At the same time, the therapy sciences should raise awareness of bio-psycho-social interdependencies in the sense of 'planetary health'. Both in research and practice, this is done by considering and respecting the animate and inanimate environment of humans and by promoting the regeneration of natural resources [15].

OT-SLT-PT research has components from natural sciences, social sciences and humanities. Therefore, all methodological approaches of observational and experimental, qualitative and quantitative research are relevant. They may also be combined as 'mixed methods' [16]. This corresponds to the principle of the appropriateness of research methods to the subject matter. Participatory and action research approaches are also pursued, as person-centred care implies participation and decision-making power of service users in all phases of the therapeutic process.

Basic conditions for effective therapeutic sciences

Inter- and intra-professional exchange and interdisciplinary co-operation are the basis for future-oriented therapy sciences. OT-SLT-PT research in Germany must therefore meet scientific standards [17] and be capable of engaging in international scientific discourse. Publications in English language expand the potential for co-operation. National and international conferences and symposia allow for linking up with other research and teaching institutions or commercial partners, in order to gain access to research funding. At the international level, the scientifically independent 'body of knowledge' of OT-SLT-PT is firm and recognised. This is due to the academisation and professionalisation of therapists being significantly more advanced in other countries, as compared to Germany. Furthermore, the knowledge transfer of research findings into practice must be accompanied by dedicated implementation research in the context of the respective national healthcare system.

Concerted action in health, research and education policy is required to create better structural conditions for the therapeutic sciences [18] [19]. These include therapy-specific funding lines and adequate financing, scientific qualification opportunities (doctorates), promotion of young researchers (postdoctoral positions) and more dedicated research time by reducing teaching loads. This is essential for therapeutic disciplines and professions to develop independently alongside the medical profession [20]. Quality assurance and priority-setting for therapeutic research at national level must ultimately be led by the professionals themselves, by their scientific associations and research organisations.

Research in outpatient therapeutic practice, considering intersectoral interfaces of care, is urgently needed in Germany. The most important prerequisite for this kind of research is the full academisation of occupational therapy, speech/language therapy and physiotherapy practitioners across the country. This will enable effective, science-based practice to actually improve the processes and outcomes of care for the population.

The Hochschulverbund Gesundheitsfachberufe (HVG) e.V. represents the universities offering therapy degree programmes in Germany. It calls for the full academisation of the professions of occupational therapy, speech/language therapy and physiotherapy (OT-SLT-PT). Besides university-based training (academic teaching), it therefore advocates for the processing of therapeutic research needs, and for research being conducted by members of these professions. The three young disciplines have joint under the umbrella of the HVG and shaped the term 'therapy sciences'.

This position paper is supported by the following organisations and institutions (as of 2025/04/02):

- Deutsches Netzwerk Gesundheitskompetenz e.V. (DNGK) [German Network for Health Literacy]
- Physio Deutschland – Deutscher Verband für Physiotherapie e.V. [German Association for Physiotherapy]
- Deutscher Verband Ergotherapie e.V. (DVE) [German Association of Occupational Therapy]
- Deutscher Bundesverband der Atem-, Sprech- und Stimmlehrer/innen (dba), Lehrervereinigung Schlaffhorst-Andersen e.V. [German Federal Association of Breathing, Speech and Voice Therapists, Schlaffhorst-Andersen Teachers' Association]
- Deutscher Bundesverband für akademische Sprachtherapie und Logopädie e.V. (dbs) [German Federal Association for Academic Speech and Language Therapy]
- Deutscher Bundesverband für Logopädie e.V. (dbl) [German Federal Association for Speech Therapy]

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